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URBAN GREEN SPACES

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Abstract: Nowadays, urban design without green spaces is inconceivable. Environmental, social, and economic benefits generated by green spaces are essential to maintain the health and quality of life of the population and to control pollution. Therefore, urban planners and city leaders should know the interactions between the features of green spaces, the sociodemographic characteristics of users, and the type of use. In addition, in some studies, noise was found to be an essential factor in the perception of these green spaces. For this purpose, surveys and sound measurements were carried out simultaneously in different locations of the main green spaces of Cáceres city. The results of this study show that noise satisfaction has the greatest significant relationship with overall satisfaction with green spaces. Different features, including satisfaction with the absence of noise, can explain 71.4% of the overall satisfaction. Road traffic is the most annoying sound source, but the degree of noise annoyance is lower than that estimated for other urban environments with similar sound levels. Walking and talking activities, emotions of fear and irritability, and interruptions to conversation are most often affected by noise in these urban environments. Another conclusion obtained is that the highest significant correlation coefficients are between noise perception by users and both the equivalent continuous linear weighted sound level and sharpness. Lastly, the green-space use determines differences and significant relationships with the sociodemographic characteristics. Also, the places in green spaces where people frequently perform walking and relaxation activities have the lowest sound levels. Therefore, noise is a statistically relevant factor to be considered in the design of green spaces.

Response to Reviewers: Response to Reviewers: The authors are grateful to the reviewers because their useful comments and suggestions aimed improving our work. We addressed every point item by item in the letter we received from the Editor. The responses are in blue below.

Reviewers/Editor comments:

“Relationships among satisfaction, noise perception, and use of urban green spaces”

Highlights

- Noise is the most influential factor in the evaluation of an urban green space.
- Road traffic remains the fundamental source of noise in urban green spaces.
- For the same sound level, noise annoyance is lower than in other urban areas.
- L_{eq} (dB) and sharpness proved to be good estimators of noise perception.
- The lower the noise, the higher the frequency of relaxation and walking activities.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 In the last decades, there has been a clear trend toward the depopulation of rural areas
3 and increasing concentration of human beings in cities. Currently 57% of the population
4 live in agglomerations having populations in excess of 300000 people, and it is
5 estimated that by the year 2030, 62% of the global population will live in cities (UN,
6 2014).

7 The rapid growth of cities has brought social, economic, and environmental challenges
8 (EC, 2000). Five objectives in the environmental dimension have been defined for a
9 European vision of tomorrow's cities: mitigate and adapt to climate change; protect,
10 restore, and enhance biodiversity and ecosystems; reduce pollution; manage natural
11 materials resources sustainably and prevent waste; and protect, preserve, and manage
12 water resources (RFSC, 2016). Populations are living in environments with increasing
13 pollution, intense heat, habitat loss, declining biodiversity, and noise (EEA, 2014, 2016;
14 IEAGHG, 2016; RFSC, 2016). Approximately seven million people died in 2012 due to
15 exposure to air pollution (WHO, 2014), and 60000 disability-adjusted life years are lost
16 through ischaemic heart disease due to environmental noise (WHO, 2011). There is a
17 critical need to find ways to reduce health risks and improve the wellbeing of citizens.

18 Studies from numerous fields have analysed the benefits provided by urban green
19 spaces in cities and they are related with three key values: social, economic, and
20 environmental (Chiesura, 2011; Sander, 2015; Scopelliti et al., 2016; Szeremeta and
21 Zannin, 2013). Urban green spaces play an important role from a social perspective by
22 promoting physical activity, allowing rest or relaxation and increasing social interaction
23 (Dadvand et al., 2016; Kaczynski et al., 2008; Mass et al., 2009; Peters et al., 2010).
24 They therefore help to facilitate active lifestyles and emotions of restoration while

1 reducing stress and social isolation in urban environments (Combes et al., 2010; Grahn
2 and Stigsdotter, 2003, 2010; Jay and Schraml, 2009). Urban green spaces also benefit
3 local residents and communities economically. Aesthetic and recreational values of
4 urban green spaces increase the attractiveness of a city and promote it as a tourist
5 destination, thus generating employment and revenue (Jim and Chen, 2006). Water and
6 vegetation also increase property values (Luttik, 2000; Sander and Haight, 2012). The
7 other key value of urban green spaces is environmental benefits, such as counteracting
8 the urban heat island effect (Doick et al., 2014; Feyisa et al., 2014), reducing air
9 pollution (Cohen et al., 2014; Yin et al., 2011), mitigating runoff (Xiao et al., 1998), and
10 maintaining urban biodiversity (Alvey, 2006; Paker et al., 2014). Consequently, due to
11 the range of social and environmental services they afford, urban green spaces are a
12 public good and their availability is a core indicator for a sustainability profile (EC,
13 2000).

14 Noise pollution ranks second among a series of environmental stressors in terms of
15 public health impacts (WHO, 2011). The existence of “quiet areas” is among the
16 objectives of the European noise policy (EC, 2002). However, some studies show that
17 noise levels in urban green spaces are not significantly lower than those in the typical
18 home environment (Cohen et al., 2014; Martínez Suarez and Moreno Jiménez, 2013;
19 Lam et al., 2005; Tse et al., 2012; Zannin et al., 2006).

20 Urban green space functionality and outcomes are closely related to their features
21 (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2015). Recent studies relate some features or uses of urban
22 green spaces to the benefits they provide (Dadvand et al., 2016; Scopelliti et al., 2016).
23 However, studies analysing the relative contributions of the different features of green
24 spaces to the overall explanation of their functionality remain scarce.

1 In this study, the features of green spaces were evaluated through the perceptions of
2 users and, from these perceptions, their relationships with respect to the overall
3 satisfaction with the green areas were analysed. The extent to which a user takes into
4 account the features of a green space when giving it an overall assessment is a very
5 important aspect for urban planners and city leaders. Thus, core indicators for a local
6 sustainability profile were evaluated: availability of local public green areas and
7 citizens' satisfaction with the local community (EC, 2000).

8 Because of the importance of noise satisfaction in the overall assessment of green areas,
9 another objective of the study was to analyse the annoyance caused by noise sources
10 and their effects on users' activities and attitudes.

11 Finally, satisfaction with the features of green spaces, the annoyance caused by noise,
12 and the effects of noise were related to the sociodemographic characteristics of the
13 users. In addition, the relationship between these aspects and the activities carried out
14 by users in urban green spaces was analysed. These results could also be used by urban
15 planners when designing green spaces for certain uses.

16 **2. Methodology**

17 **2.1. Study area**

18 The study was carried out in green spaces of Cáceres, a medium-sized city located in the
19 southwest of Spain, whose proportion of green area per inhabitant is approximately 16.6
20 m² per inhabitant. This proportion is one of the highest in the country and is greater than
21 the range of 10–15 m² per inhabitant recommended by the World Health Organization
22 (Brebba et al., 2010).

1 The following urban green areas were selected for this study: Cánovas, Principe,
 2 Valhondo, Fernando Turégano, Fray Pacífico, Perú, and Rodeo. Locations and aerial
 3 photos of the green spaces are shown in Fig. 1. The green spaces were chosen on the
 4 basis of location, size, and year of inauguration (see Table 1).

Urban green spaces	Year of inauguration	Area (hm²)	Distance from the city centre (km)
Cánovas	1895	2.1	Downtown
Príncipe	1970	22.0	0.5
Valhondo	2001	2.2	1.3
Fernando Turégano	2000	3.2	2.0
Fray Pacífico	1998	1.6	1.0
Perú	2002	1.5	0.8
Rodeo	2001	10.6	0.8

5 **Table 1.** Year of inauguration, area, and distance from the city centre of the green
 6 spaces.

7 These green spaces are located in densely populated urban areas and are representative
 8 of the different districts. They are popular green spaces frequently visited by citizens in
 9 Cáceres. The selected green spaces were large enough for the activities analysed later in
 10 the survey. The age of the green spaces made it possible to analyse the evolution of
 11 satisfaction regarding the features evaluated in previous studies.

1

Fig. 1. Map of Cáceres city (Spain) with location of the selected green spaces and

3

sampled sites (images from Google Earth).

4

2.2. Surveys

5

A cross-sectional study was carried out during 2014 by means of questionnaires

6

administered during daytime to a random sample of adult visitors to the seven urban

7

green spaces selected. Face-to-face interviews were conducted by trained interviewers.

8

During the survey, respondents were informed about the objectives of the study and the

1 time required to complete the questionnaire (about 10 minutes). A total of 182
 2 completed questionnaires were used for this study. The percentage of respondents
 3 compared to the total number of citizens was similar to that used in recent studies
 4 (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2015; Kaczynski et al., 2008) with a sufficient statistical
 5 power (Fritz and Mackinnon et al., 2007). The questionnaires were well distributed in
 6 terms of district, sampling points, size of green space, and number of visitors. In this
 7 way, the sample presented sociodemographic characteristics representative of the
 8 population resident in Cáceres (see Table 2).

Variable	Sample (%)	Cáceres (%) (INE, 2015)
Age		
18–25 years	17.0	9.8
26–35 years	15.4	17.8
36–45 years	23.6	20.8
46–55 years	12.1	20.0
56–65 years	11.0	13.7
>66 years	20.9	17.9
Sex		
Male	47.3	48.2
Female	52.7	51.8
Education		
Missing	8.1	8.8
Primary or secondary school	37.5	35.2
Highschool	24.5	25.3
Degree	29.9	30.8
Work activity		
Worker	41.8	40.9
Unemployed	15.4	14.2
Retired	17.0	16.4
Homemaker	16.5	7.5
Student	9.3	21.0
Main activity in the green space ^a		
Reading	3.3	
Taking children out	20.9	
Relaxing	25.3	
Exercising	25.3	
Walking	60.4	
Talking	54.9	

9 ^a Percentage of the sample whose activity is carried out “very often” or “often”

10 **Table 2.** Sociodemographic and green-space-use characteristics of the sample.

1 In each urban green space, the sites most frequented by visitors were selected to conduct
2 the surveys and the acoustic measurements (see Fig. 1). Interviews and acoustics
3 measurements were carried out simultaneously.

4 In the survey, three dimensions were analysed: satisfaction (12 items, $\alpha_{\text{Cronbach}} = 0.79$),
5 noise annoyance (8 items, $\alpha_{\text{Cronbach}} = 0.70$), and effects of noise (14 items, $\alpha_{\text{Cronbach}} =$
6 0.81). The items were rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (“not at all” or
7 “never”) to 4 (“a lot” or “very often”).

8 In the first dimension, the satisfaction with the features of urban green spaces was
9 analysed. The following items were evaluated: cleanliness, air quality, noise, aesthetics,
10 safety, users, conservation, location, size, groves, and shade. These features were
11 selected due to their relationship with social, economic, or environmental aspects that
12 influence the overall satisfaction with green spaces. Overall satisfaction was also
13 evaluated in one item. The cleanliness, aesthetics, and conservation along with
14 environmental features such as groves have an influence on the visual assessment of the
15 green space. In turn, these features influence the overall valuation and can influence the
16 valuation of other environmental features such as noise (Carles et al., 1999; Preis et al.,
17 2015). Noise, air quality, groves, and shade are features to be considered in assessing
18 the environmental benefit of green spaces, as recent studies have shown (Jabben et al.,
19 2015, Shen et al., 2016). Besides, social and design aspects such as security, users, size,
20 and location should be considered. Recent studies show that the locations and
21 proportion of green spaces have a significant influence on healthy habits (Dadvand et
22 al., 2016; Scopelliti et al., 2016; Shen and Candice Lung, 2016). However, the function
23 and assessment of these features may be influenced by social characteristics, such as the
24 relationship with users or security (López Barrios, 2001).

1 Also, in 2007–2008, the satisfaction dimension was studied in the same green spaces
2 using the sampling procedure employed in this study and interviewing 234 users. The
3 results of that analysis showed that noise was one of the environmental features with
4 which users were less satisfied (see Table 3). Therefore, because of these results and the
5 current interest in this environmental pollutant, in the present study, noise annoyance
6 and noise effect dimensions were analysed.

7 On the noise-annoyance dimension, the annoyance caused by the main sound sources in
8 urban green spaces, such as road traffic and sounds from people (voices, children,
9 construction sites, maintenance services), was evaluated (Benfield et al., 2010;
10 Szeremeta and Zannin, 2009; Torija et al., 2014). In addition, sounds from animals and
11 water, which are features of these urban spaces, were evaluated (Barrigón Morillas et
12 al., 2013). Lastly in this dimension, users were asked about the overall noise annoyance
13 in urban green spaces.

14 With regard to the noise effects dimension, the frequency of noise-induced emotions
15 (irritability, anxiety, disorientation, fear, earache), the frequency with which the
16 activities carried out in green spaces (talking, reading, relaxing, walking, exercising)
17 were disturbed by noise, and the actions induced by noise (increasing conversation
18 volume, interrupting conversation, leaving the site, leaving the urban green space) were
19 evaluated.

20 Finally, the sociodemographic characteristics and green-space use were registered.

1 **2.3. Acoustic data**

2 As indicated above, the sites most frequented by visitors were selected for performing
3 the surveys and acoustic measurements simultaneously. The number of sampling points
4 was determined by the size of green spaces and the variety of soundscapes. This is
5 similar to that used in recent studies (Szeremeta and Zannin, 2015; Paneto et al., 2017).
6 Figure 1 shows the locations of sampling points in each urban green space.

7 The measurement campaign was carried out from 10:00 to 21:00 h during week days
8 and weekends. The sound levels were measured with a Brüel & Kjaer 2238 sound-level
9 meter and a binaural recording device (Noise Book from Head Acoustics). Thus, the
10 sound descriptors L_{Aeq} , L_{Amax} , L_{Amin} , L_{A1} , L_{A5} , L_{A10} , L_{A90} , L_{A95} , L_{A99} , and L_{Cpeak} were
11 registered. These sound descriptors have been used in numerous current studies to
12 characterize sound environments (Szeremeta and Zannin, 2009; Torija et al., 2014; Tse
13 et al., 2012; Yu and Kang, 2014). Also, the sound descriptors L_{Aeq} and L_{eq} were
14 registered with a binaural recording device, which also analysed psychoacoustic
15 indicators such as loudness and sharpness. Some authors indicate that binaural
16 recording is more useful than other methods because it is possible to recreate the spatial
17 characteristics of the sound environment (Jeon et al., 2013).

18 Measurements followed ISO 1996–2 standard guidelines (Barrigón Morillas et al.,
19 2016; ISO 1996–2, 2007), which meant that the microphone was placed at a height of
20 1.5 m in free-field conditions. At each sampling point, a 10-minute measurement was
21 performed every time a survey was conducted. The duration of sound measurement was
22 considered sufficient considering previous studies carried out in urban parks (Axelsson
23 et al., 2014; Jabben et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2014; Lobo Soares and Bento Coelho, 2016;
24 Szeremeta and Zannin, 2009; Zannin et al., 2006).

1 **2.4. Statistical analysis**

2 Firstly, a descriptive analysis of the average valuations (mean and median) given by
3 users to the items of the three dimensions analysed was carried out. These results show
4 the users' perceptions of the urban green spaces. In the case of the satisfaction
5 dimension, the results were compared with the average values obtained for the years
6 2007–2008. For this purpose, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test was used because
7 the variables were categorical.

8 Also, within the descriptive or exploratory analysis, a hierarchical cluster analysis was
9 carried out. This procedure attempts to identify natural groupings (or clusters) within a
10 variable set (Aldenderfer and Blashfield, 1984). Hierarchical cluster analysis first
11 separates each variable into a cluster by itself. At each stage of the analysis, the two
12 nearest clusters (the most similar clusters in terms of distance) are joined until all of the
13 variables are joined in a complete classification tree. This tree diagram is called
14 dendrogram. In the dendrogram, the clusters are represented by horizontal lines and the
15 stages of the merger by vertical lines (see Fig. 2). The separation between the stages of
16 the merger is proportional to the distance at which the clusters are joining at that stage.
17 However, the distances are not represented in their original scale but in a standardised
18 scale of 25 points (rescaled distance). As in previous studies (Brambilla et al., 2013;
19 Nilsson and Berglund, 2006; Rey Gozalo and Barrigón Morillas, 2017), the merger was
20 stopped when the clusters which were going to be joined were significantly more distant
21 than those previously merged. Thus, the rescaled merger distance was lower than 15 in
22 Fig. 2(a) and it was 15 in Fig. 2(b). There are different types of measures to estimate the
23 distance between variables or clusters. Also there are different cluster methods. Cluster
24 method defines the rules for cluster formation and the measure defines the formula for
25 calculating distance among clusters. Ward's method was used in this study. In this

1 method, at each step, the two clusters that merge are those that result in the smallest
2 increase in the overall sum of the squared of the differences, within each cluster, of each
3 individual to the centroid of the cluster (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014). Kuiper and
4 Fisher (1975) proved that Ward's method carried out a better classification than other
5 methods. Therefore, this hierarchical method is one of the most used. For example,
6 Brambilla et al. (2013) and Nilsson and Berglund (2006) have used Ward's method in
7 studies performed in urban parks. With respect to the measure to estimate the distance,
8 the chi-squared measure was used in this study because the variables are categorical
9 (Greenacre, 1988; Hussain and Asghar, 2016). The items are ranging from 0 (“not at
10 all” or “never”) to 4 (“a lot” or “very often”).

11 Secondly, the relationships between the different variables registered in the study were
12 analysed. First, within each dimension, the relationship of each item with its overall
13 valuation (satisfaction or noise annoyance) was analysed. For this purpose, bivariate and
14 partial correlations (Kendall's tau-b) were used. The partial correlations show the
15 relationship between two variables controlling the possible effects of the rest of the
16 variables in the same dimension (Kim, 2015). In the case of the satisfaction dimension,
17 a multinomial logistic regression model was created from variables (features) which had
18 a significant relationship with the overall satisfaction. Methods for stepwise selection of
19 variables (forward and backward) and the likelihood ratio tests to check the contribution
20 of each variable to the model were used. Also, the results obtained in the hierarchical
21 cluster analysis (features within the same cluster have a similar frequency with respect
22 to the users' valuations and, therefore, could have collinearities) and in the partial
23 correlation (features with a higher correlation coefficient with overall satisfaction after
24 eliminating the possible influence of the other features) were considered in the selection
25 of predictors. For each variable, the $-2 \log$ -likelihood is computed for the reduced

1 model; that is, a model without the variable. The chi-squared statistic is the difference
2 between the -2 log-likelihoods of the reduced model and the final model. If the
3 significance of the test is less than 0.05, the variable contributes to the model. Also, the
4 likelihood ratio test shows if the final model fits the data better than a null model. For
5 the final model, chi-squared statistic is the difference between the -2 log-likelihoods of
6 the null and final models. If the significance level of the test is less than 0.05, the final
7 model is outperforming the null.

8 Also, within the analysis of the relationships between variables, the mean values of the
9 subjective perceptions to the noise in the sampled points were related to the levels of the
10 registered sound indicators (Rho Spearman). Finally, the correlation between the items
11 registered in the three dimensions and the sociodemographic characteristics and green
12 space use (Kendall's tau-b) was analysed.

13 **3. Results and discussion**

14 **3.1. Satisfaction with urban green spaces**

15 Table 3 shows the development of the level of user satisfaction with the features of
16 green spaces of Cáceres. Currently there is a very good perception of the size and
17 distribution of green spaces in the urban area, with average values of 3.7 and 3.6 for
18 location and size, respectively. These valuations have increased compared to the study
19 performed in 2007–2008 because of improvements in use options (creation of play and
20 sports areas) and because of the population growth in the peripheral neighbourhoods.

Features	Level of satisfaction (Scale 0–4)				P-value ^a	Correlation with overall satisfaction in 2014 R ^b
	2014		2007–2008			
	Mean	Median	Mean	Median		
Cleanliness	3.0	3	2.9	3	> 0.05	0.37 ^{***}
Air quality	2.7	3	2.6	3	> 0.05	0.40 ^{***}
Noise	2.4	2	2.4	3	> 0.05	0.42 ^{***}
Aesthetics	3.2	3	2.9	3	< 0.001	0.34 ^{***}
Safety	3.5	4	2.5	3	< 0.001	0.21 ^{**}
User	3.0	3	2.6	3	< 0.001	0.22 ^{***}
Conservation	3.2	3	2.9	3	< 0.001	0.32 ^{***}
Location	3.7	4	3.0	3	< 0.001	0.16 [*]
Size	3.6	4	3.0	3	< 0.001	0.25 ^{***}
Shade	3.2	3	2.1	2	< 0.001	0.30 ^{***}
Groves	3.2	3	2.2	2	< 0.001	0.28 ^{***}
Overall	3.1	3	3.0	3	> 0.05	–

1 ^aMann-Whitney test

2 ^bCorrelation coefficient (Kendall’s tau–b).

3 *Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

4 **Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

5 ***Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

6 **Table 3.** Average level of satisfaction with the features of urban green spaces, analysis
7 of the significance of the differences in average values of satisfaction between the years
8 2007–2008 and 2014, and bivariate correlations between the features of and overall
9 satisfaction with urban green spaces in 2014.

10 The age of green spaces is reflected by the average satisfaction with the shade and
11 groves, valued at 3.2. The satisfaction with these features has increased significantly in
12 the last six years. Also, green spaces have water fountains and their own gardening and
13 cleaning service, which contribute valuations of 3 (“quite”) to 4 (“a lot”) to the average
14 satisfaction with regard to the features of aesthetics, cleaning, and conservation.

15 At the entrance to the green spaces, the rules of behaviour and the regulations regarding
16 opening and closing are shown. This contributes to the fact that direct and indirect
17 relations between users and safety can be considered quite good, with ratings between 3
18 and 4. Some incidents prior to 2008 led the council to limit the access to the green

1 spaces and increase their security. Perhaps this is the reason why safety is one feature
 2 whose satisfaction has most increased over the years analysed.

3 However, users have lower satisfaction (from “moderate” to “quite”) with the aspects
 4 related to environmental contamination, giving valuations of 2.7 for air quality and 2.4
 5 for the absence of noise. Also, these valuations do not show significant differences from
 6 those registered six years ago (see Table 3). Noise was also the worst feature valued
 7 with respect to other features analysed in Italian and Brazilian parks (Brambilla et al.,
 8 2013; Szeremeta and Zannin, 2015). In a hierarchical cluster analysis, for a rescaled
 9 distance of 10, both variables form an independent group [see Fig. 2(a)]. However, the
 10 mean satisfaction with the absence of noise is significantly lower than the mean
 11 satisfaction with air quality (p-value < 0.01 according to the Mann-Whitney test). The
 12 fact that valuation regarding noise has not increased in the last six years, even though
 13 features such as groves have significantly increased user satisfaction, may contradict the
 14 results of other studies that show a relation between noise perception and groves (Hong
 15 and Jeon, 2013; Liu et al., 2014).

16

17 **Fig 2.** Dendrograms obtained from hierarchical cluster analysis (Ward’s method). The
 18 inputs to the analysis were the satisfaction with the features of urban green spaces (a)
 19 and the annoyance with the sound sources (b).

1 Next, the extent to which the features are considered by users of green spaces in making
2 their overall assessments of the green space was analysed. This aspect may be important
3 for urban planners, city leaders, and environmental engineers.

4 As a result of this study, all features considered have a significant influence on overall
5 satisfaction (see Table 3). Therefore, user satisfaction with each feature of the green
6 space contributes to increased overall satisfaction. It should be noted that the features
7 can be ranked in descending order of intensity of correlation with the overall
8 satisfaction as follows: noise, air quality, cleanliness, aesthetics, and conservation.
9 Therefore, the features related to environmental pollution (noise and air quality) are
10 those that have a greater positive correlation with respect to the overall satisfaction with
11 the green space and, secondly, the features related to the care and design of the green
12 space (cleaning, aesthetics, and conservation). Jeon et al (2011) registered a higher
13 correlation coefficient between “acoustic comfort” and “overall impression” in the
14 largest city park in Seoul than that obtained between “visual image” and “overall
15 impression”. Also, similar results have been obtained in studies performed in urban
16 open public spaces (Preis et al., 2015; Rey Gozalo and Barrigón Morillas, 2017; Kang
17 and Zhang, 2010).

18 Moreover, an analysis of the partial correlation between the satisfaction with features
19 and the overall satisfaction with the green space was carried out. The partial correlation
20 coefficients obtained are shown in Fig. 3. In this partial correlation analysis, the
21 possible influence of the other features on the bivariate correlation analysis was
22 removed (Kim, 2015). This analysis was carried out because some features had a similar
23 distribution with respect to the users’ valuations. Therefore, users of the green spaces
24 could be establishing relationships between the different features of green spaces. In a
25 hierarchical cluster analysis using the Ward’s method with the chi-squared measure for

- 1 a rescaled distance of 10, four main groups were differentiated: air quality–noise,
- 2 shade–groves, users, and other features [see Fig. 2(a)].

3

4 **Fig. 3.** Kendall's partial correlation coefficients among items of satisfaction, noise
 5 annoyance, and noise effect dimensions. * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$; ** significant at $p \leq$
 6 0.01 ; *** significant at $p \leq 0.001$; n.s. non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

7 Figure 3 shows that groves, safety, location, aesthetic and size do not have a significant
 8 partial correlation with the overall satisfaction and that noise is the feature that has a
 9 higher coefficient of partial correlation with the overall satisfaction with green spaces.
 10 Also, it should be noted that it has a greater influence than air quality. Perhaps the fact
 11 that satisfaction with the absence of noise has not increased since 2007–2008 influenced
 12 the fact that there is no significant variation of the overall satisfaction with the green
 13 spaces. Although the aesthetic loses the significant relation with respect to the overall

1 satisfaction, other features related to the visual component (cleanliness and
 2 conservation) have a significant correlation coefficient. This correlation coefficient is
 3 similar to that obtained for the noise and air quality (see Fig. 3).

4 Then, a multivariate analysis was carried out to analyse how the set of features explains
 5 the users' overall perceptions of the urban green spaces. The results of the multinomial
 6 logistic regression are shown in Tables 4, 5, and 6. According to the likelihood ratio
 7 tests, the noise, users, conservation, and shade features contributed significantly to
 8 explaining the overall variability of the regression model (see Table 4). These features
 9 also have the highest partial correlation within each cluster [see Fig. 2(a) and Fig. 3].
 10 The regression coefficients of these features and their significance are shown in Table 5.
 11 The values 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4 shown in Tables 5 and 6 are the values of the five-point
 12 Likert scale used in the survey where 0 is "nothing satisfied" and 4 is "very satisfied".
 13 Consequently, the visual, sound and functional aspects are included in the regression
 14 model (Liu et al., 2013). The regression model generated has a McFadden R-squared of
 15 0.41. If the McFadden R-squared value is higher than 0.40, the multinomial logistic
 16 regression is considered to have an excellent fit quality (Pando Fernández and San
 17 Martín Fernández, 2004). There are different current survey studies that obtain similar
 18 R-squared values (De Valck et al., 2014; Lovejoy et al., 2010; Sirina et al., 2017).

		- 2 log likelihood	Chi- squared	Sig.	R-squared McFadden
Variables	Noise (1)	179.1	63.7	< 0.001	-
	Conservation (2)	157.3	41.8	< 0.001	-
	Users (3)	152.1	36.7	0.002	-
	Shade (4)	138.0	22.6	0.032	-
Model	Final (1-2-3-4)	115.5	161.1	< 0.001	0.41

19 **Table 4.** Likelihood ratio tests and model fitting information.

	Overall Satisfaction ^a							
	Value = 0		Value = 1		Value = 2		Value = 3	
	B ^b	P-value ^c	B ^b	P-value ^c	B ^b	P-value ^c	B ^b	P-value ^c
Intercept	-23.3	> 0.05	-55.2	> 0.05	-36.7	> 0.05	-2.6	< 0.001
Noise = 0	17.8	> 0.05	116.9	> 0.05	49.5	> 0.05	1.8	> 0.05
Noise = 1	2.1	> 0.05	44.7	> 0.05	16.1	> 0.05	3.3	< 0.01
Noise = 2	-0.8	> 0.05	54.1	> 0.05	14.8	> 0.05	2.3	< 0.001
Noise = 3	5.1	> 0.05	41.8	> 0.05	-3.8	> 0.05	1.5	< 0.05
Noise = 4	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-
User = 0	15.2	> 0.05	0.1	> 0.05	24.9	> 0.05	13.4	> 0.05
User = 1	1.9	> 0.05	-57.1	> 0.05	2.8	> 0.05	2.2	< 0.01
User = 2	8.9	> 0.05	-15.4	> 0.05	3.0	< 0.05	1.3	< 0.05
User = 3	0.7	> 0.05	-8.9	> 0.05	1.7	> 0.05	1.1	< 0.05
User = 4	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-
Conservation = 2	11.4	> 0.05	65.2	> 0.05	37.2	> 0.05	15.4	> 0.05
Conservation = 3	1.2	> 0.05	-0.1	> 0.05	19.2	> 0.05	0.7	< 0.05
Conservation = 4	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-
Shade = 1	11.4	> 0.05	16.4	> 0.05	17.5	> 0.05	-1.9	> 0.05
Shade = 2	0.7	> 0.05	-47.9	> 0.05	0.7	> 0.05	0.2	> 0.05
Shade = 3	7.6	> 0.05	-38.7	> 0.05	0.5	> 0.05	0.4	< 0.05
Shade = 4	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-	0 ^d	-

1 ^aThe reference category is: 4

2 ^bRegression coefficients

3 ^cWald test

4 ^dThis parameter is set to zero because it is redundant

5 **Table 5.** Parameter estimates in the multinomial logistic regression

6 Table 6 shows the practical results of using the multinomial logistic regression model.

7 The overall percentage predicted by the multinomial logistic regression is 71.4%. The

8 values of 2, 3, and 4 given by users for overall satisfaction constitute 97.3% of the

9 responses. These values are predicted at 77.3, 77.9, and 63.3%, respectively, by the

10 multivariate model (see Table 6).

Observed	Predicted					Percentage correct
	0	1	2	3	4	
0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
1	0	1	1	1	1	25.0%
2	0	0	17	5	0	77.3%
3	0	0	2	74	19	77.9%
4	0	0	0	22	38	63.3%
Overall percentage	0%	0.5%	11.0%	56.6%	31.9%	71.4%

11 **Table 6.** Percentage predicted by the multinomial logistic regression

1 The absence of noise is the environmental feature that individually has the greatest
2 correlation with the overall satisfaction that users give to Cáceres green spaces. In
3 addition, noise along with the conservation and shade features and the relation between
4 users can explain 71.4% of the overall satisfaction.

5 **3.2. Annoyance and effects of noise**

6 The annoyance and effects of noise in Cáceres green spaces are low, as shown by the
7 mean values in Table 7. The sound sources from road traffic and from users (screams
8 and children) cause the most annoyance. The walking and talking activities, the
9 emotions of fear and irritability, and the action of interrupting conversations are the
10 most often affected by noise.

11 Figure 4 shows the variability of the equivalent continuous sound level (dBA) registered
12 in the sampling points of urban green spaces. These values are similar to the values
13 registered in the neighbourhood streets of other Spanish cities (Rey Gozalo et al.,
14 2013a, 2013b, 2015a). However, although road traffic was the most annoying sound
15 source for the users of the green spaces, the degree of annoyance was lower than that
16 estimated in neighbourhood streets (Rey Gozalo et al., 2012, 2014, 2016). Also, the
17 variability of the equivalent continuous sound level (dBA) is similar to the variability
18 registered in the urban parks of other cities in the world (Axelsson et al., 2014;
19 Brambilla et al., 2016; Cohen et al., 2014; Jabben et al., 2015; Lobo Soares and Bento
20 Coelho, 2016; Srezemeta and Zannin, 2015; Tse et al., 2012).

	Annoyance/ frequency (scale 0–4)		Correlation with overall noise annoyance	Correlation with noise sensitivity
	Mean	Median	R ^a	R ^a
Sound sources				
Construction	0.4	0	0.23 ^{***}	0.22 ^{***}
Screams	1.2	1	0.40 ^{***}	0.17 [*]
Animals	0.9	1	0.19 ^{**}	0.08 ^{n.s.}
Maintenance	0.7	0	0.17 ^{**}	0.20 ^{**}
Road traffic	1.3	1	0.42 ^{***}	0.07 ^{n.s.}
Children	1.1	1	0.32 ^{***}	0.07 ^{n.s.}
Water	0.4	0	0.14 [*]	0.12 ^{n.s.}
Overall noise annoyance	1.3	1	–	0.21 ^{**}
Affected activities				
Talking	1.1	1	0.41 ^{***}	0.14 [*]
Reading	0.1	0	0.06 ^{n.s.}	0.03 ^{n.s.}
Relaxing	0.6	0	0.28 ^{***}	0.12 ^{n.s.}
Walking	0.8	1	0.41 ^{***}	0.17 [*]
Exercising	0.3	0	0.10 ^{n.s.}	0.03 ^{n.s.}
Emotions				
Irritability	0.6	0	0.36 ^{***}	0.32 ^{***}
Anxiety	0.1	0	0.16 [*]	0.24 ^{**}
Disorientation	0.1	0	0.19 ^{**}	0.19 [*]
Fear	1.1	1	0.33 ^{***}	0.14 ^{n.s.}
Earache	0.4	0	0.31 ^{***}	0.31 ^{***}
Actions				
Increasing conversation volume	0.3	0	0.02 ^{n.s.}	–0.02 ^{n.s.}
Interrupting the conversation	1.2	1	0.49 ^{***}	0.17 [*]
Leaving the site	0.5	0	0.18 ^{**}	0.20 ^{**}
Leaving the green space	0.1	0	0.17 [*]	0.14 ^{n.s.}

1 ^a Correlation coefficient (Kendall’s tau-b).

2 ^{*} Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3 ^{**} Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.

4 ^{***} Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

5 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).

6 **Table 6.** Average level of annoyance with the sound sources in urban green spaces and
7 average level of frequency of noise effects on users. The bivariate correlation between
8 annoyance with sound sources and the effects of noise with respect to the overall
9 annoyance and the sensitivity of the users is also shown.

Fig. 4. Box plot of the equivalent sound level measured in the green spaces of Cáceres.

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The degree of annoyance with the different sound sources has a positive correlation with the overall noise annoyance (see Table 7). Also the overall noise annoyance has a significant correlation with the frequency of most effects caused by noise. However, although noise sensitivity has been used in recent studies as a predictor of noise annoyance and noise effects (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2015; Stansfeld and Shipley, 2015), its relationship with the evaluated variables has a lower correlation coefficient. In addition, noise sensitivity is not significantly correlated with some of the most annoying sources (road traffic and children) or with some of the most frequent emotions (fear). In the study by Dzhambov and Dimitrova (2015), an average annoyance higher than that found in this study was registered (a value of 5.5 on a scale of 0 to 10). Also, in the study by Stansfeld and Shipley (2015), negative health effects were more frequent than in this study. Therefore, noise sensitivity may not be a good predictor of the effects of this factor in urban environments where noise effects are low.

1 Thus, as in other urban environments, road traffic is the source that produces the highest
2 degree of annoyance and has the greatest correlation coefficient with the overall
3 annoyance. Also, the annoyance caused by the noise produced by users (children and
4 screams) is relevant, as happens in urban environments where the traffic is restricted
5 (Gómez Escobar et al., 2012; Barrigón Morillas et al., 2013; Rey Gozalo and Barrigón
6 Morillas, 2017) and in public areas (Paneto et al., 2017). The most annoying sound
7 sources form an independent cluster according to the results of the hierarchical analysis
8 shown in Fig. 2(b). Within this cluster and removing the possible relations with the
9 other sound sources, road traffic is the source that has a greater coefficient of partial
10 correlation with the overall annoyance (see Fig. 3). Other sound sources, including
11 water, animals, maintenance, and construction, rarely or never produce discomfort.
12 Some current studies show that water sounds and ratings of soundscape quality are not
13 directly related (Axelsson et al., 2014; Hong and Jeon, 2013). Also, although birdsong
14 could improve the perception of the soundscape (Hong and Jeon, 2013), the
15 predominant animal sound in Cáceres green spaces is associated with dogs barking,
16 which has a negative effect. Thus, in the cluster formed by the animals–water–
17 construction–maintenance sound sources [see Fig. 2(b)], annoyance with animals is the
18 only sound source that has a significant partial correlation with the overall annoyance
19 caused by noise (see Fig. 3).

20 The average annoyance with the sound sources group perceived in urban green spaces
21 reported by the respondents is similar to the perceived annoyance with road traffic (see
22 Table 7). Despite the low value of overall annoyance (1.3 in a range of 0 to 4), this
23 value is similar to the value registered in the old town of the same city, where road
24 traffic is restricted (Rey Gozalo and Barrigón Morillas, 2017). The coefficient of
25 correlation between overall annoyance and annoyance with road traffic is the highest

1 among the sound sources analysed and this would not be significantly increased in a
2 multivariate model. In turn, the overall annoyance is also negatively correlated with
3 satisfaction with the absence of noise (a Kendall's bivariate correlation coefficient of –
4 0.26 with a p-value lower than 0.001).

5 Due to the low annoyance values caused by noise, low values of the frequency of effects
6 on activities, emotions caused, and actions taken by users of green spaces to deal with
7 the environmental noise were obtained. The values obtained ranged from 0.1 to 1.2 (see
8 Table 7). The most affected activities are walking and talking, which coincide with the
9 activities most frequently performed by users in green spaces (see Table 2). For this
10 reason, the action most frequently induced among users by noise is interruption of
11 conversations. Regarding users' emotions, the most frequently reported are fear and
12 irritability. Also, the main reaction to noise exposure in Brazilian urban areas was
13 irritability (Paneto et al., 2017). It should be noted that the activities, emotions, and
14 actions that have a higher frequency of occurrence have a very significant correlation
15 with the overall noise annoyance (see Table 7). In a partial correlation analysis (see Fig.
16 3), some of the relations would cease to be significant because of the possible relation
17 between the effects analysed (e.g. talking). However, the higher partial correlation
18 coefficients also coincide with the effects most frequently reported by users (see Fig. 3
19 and Table 7).

20 Then, an analysis of the relation between both the annoyance caused by noise sources
21 and the effects caused by noise and the registered sound indicators was carried out (see
22 Table 8). The effects caused by noise did not have a significant relationship with sound
23 levels registered at the sampling points, except for the action of leaving the site. Table 8
24 shows how levels of sound indicators related to background noise (L_{A90} , L_{A95} , L_{A99} , and
25 L_{Amin}) contribute to an increased frequency of users leaving the site. A similar result is

1 obtained with regard to annoyance caused by water sources. Therefore, perhaps the
 2 sound level produced by water sources is not a suitable alternative way to improve the
 3 perception of sound in these green spaces. In some cases, this could be because water
 4 sounds may overlap with other natural sounds, as some studies show (Axelsson et al.,
 5 2014; Hong and Jeon, 2013). Also, the results obtained for the correlation between
 6 sharpness and the action of leaving the site or the annoyance caused by water may be
 7 interesting. Perhaps some spectral characteristics associated with this sound source,
 8 which determine the background sound level in an environment with water sources or
 9 waterfalls, may not be appropriate in green spaces or at least for certain types of
 10 activities for which they are designed.

Sound indicator	Noise annoyance				Satisfaction	Noise effects
	Animals	Road traffic	Water	Overall	Noise	Leaving the site
L _{Cpeak}	-0.18 ^{n.s.}	0.34 [*]	0.09 ^{n.s.}	0.19 ^{n.s.}	-0.33 [*]	0.08 ^{n.s.}
L _{Amax}	-0.08 ^{n.s.}	0.24 ^{n.s.}	0.13 ^{n.s.}	0.12 ^{n.s.}	-0.23 ^{n.s.}	0.11 ^{n.s.}
L _{A1}	-0.24 ^{n.s.}	0.36 [*]	0.12 ^{n.s.}	0.02 ^{n.s.}	-0.22 ^{n.s.}	0.11 ^{n.s.}
L _{A5}	-0.28 ^{n.s.}	0.35 [*]	0.18 ^{n.s.}	0.06 ^{n.s.}	-0.29 ^{n.s.}	0.09 ^{n.s.}
L _{A10}	-0.30 ^{n.s.}	0.33 [*]	0.20 ^{n.s.}	0.04 ^{n.s.}	-0.29 ^{n.s.}	0.11 ^{n.s.}
L _{A50}	-0.32 ^{n.s.}	0.25 ^{n.s.}	0.26 ^{n.s.}	0.05 ^{n.s.}	-0.25 ^{n.s.}	0.26 ^{n.s.}
L _{A90}	-0.20 ^{n.s.}	0.12 ^{n.s.}	0.37 [*]	0.10 ^{n.s.}	-0.21 ^{n.s.}	0.36 [*]
L _{A95}	-0.18 ^{n.s.}	0.11 ^{n.s.}	0.40 [*]	0.10 ^{n.s.}	-0.20 ^{n.s.}	0.37 [*]
L _{A99}	-0.16 ^{n.s.}	0.10 ^{n.s.}	0.42 [*]	0.10 ^{n.s.}	-0.19 ^{n.s.}	0.38 [*]
L _{Amin}	-0.10 ^{n.s.}	0.08 ^{n.s.}	0.45 ^{**}	0.09 ^{n.s.}	-0.19 ^{n.s.}	0.40 [*]
L _{Aeq}	-0.27 ^{n.s.}	0.29 ^{n.s.}	0.24 ^{n.s.}	0.01 ^{n.s.}	-0.26 ^{n.s.}	0.23 ^{n.s.}
L _{eq} ^b	-0.42 [*]	0.60 ^{***}	0.09 ^{n.s.}	0.35 [*]	-0.63 ^{***}	0.10 ^{n.s.}
L _{Aeq} ^b	-0.24 ^{n.s.}	0.32 ^{n.s.}	0.23 ^{n.s.}	0.16 ^{n.s.}	-0.50 ^{**}	0.21 ^{n.s.}
Loudness ^b	-0.20 ^{n.s.}	0.33 ^{n.s.}	0.25 ^{n.s.}	0.18 ^{n.s.}	-0.52 ^{**}	0.27 ^{n.s.}
Sharpness ^b	-0.03 ^{n.s.}	0.10 ^{n.s.}	0.47 ^{**}	0.17 ^{n.s.}	-0.09 ^{n.s.}	0.48 ^{**}

- 11 * Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.
 12 ** Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.
 13 *** Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.
 14 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).
 15 ^b Registered with a binaural device

16 **Table 8.** Spearman's correlation coefficients among noise perception data and sound
 17 indicators.

1 The equivalent continuous linear weighted sound level registered with the binaural
2 device is the only sound indicator with a significant correlation with the overall noise
3 annoyance. In addition, this sound indicator has the highest negative correlation with
4 noise satisfaction, although in this case, the A-weighted equivalent sound level and
5 loudness (registered with the same device) have highly significant correlations. In recent
6 studies (Preis et al., 2015; Rey Gozalo et al., 2015b) the equivalent sound level also
7 explained a percentage of variability higher than some psychoacoustic indicators in the
8 assessment of soundscape. Also, this sound indicator shows the greatest significant
9 correlation with some of the sound sources that were perceived as the most annoying in
10 these environments: road traffic and animals. In the case of the animal sound source
11 coming from dogs barking, this correlation is negative. This result shows how these
12 sound sources are sporadic and can be overlapped by other predominant sources in the
13 environment. This result for the equivalent continuous linear weighted sound level is of
14 great interest and may indicate the existence of effects associated with the sound
15 spectrum, which are minimized to some extent when the A-weighted equivalent sound
16 level is taken as reference for evaluating the acoustic situation of an environment. This
17 reasoning, which considers the spectral characteristics of a sound environment to be
18 relevant to perception of it, has also been presented with respect to sharpness in the
19 previous paragraph. In Table 8, the sharpness or L_{eq} (dB) has the highest value of the
20 correlation coefficient in relation to the aspects studied. Therefore, this result may
21 indicate that the sound spectrum can be of great importance in environments with low
22 sound levels and, consequently with low levels of noise effects, if we wish to improve
23 the features of the soundscape.

1 **3.3. Sociodemographic characteristics, use of green spaces, and perception of**
2 **environment**

3 Study of the relationships between sociodemographic characteristics and the perception
4 of the features of urban environments could explain a certain percentage of their
5 variability that cannot be explained by physical variables. However, there is no clear
6 trend in the significance of the relations between these variables (Yu and Kang, 2008).
7 Generally, gender has no significant effects on sound perception (Kang and Zhang,
8 2010). This result is similar to that obtained in this study except for the annoyance with
9 the sound source coming from children (see Table 9). It is frequently women who take
10 children to green spaces (see Table 10), and because of the proximity to this sound
11 source, it is women who experience greater annoyance. Therefore, this significant
12 difference between genders is caused by the use of the green space.

13 Age, level of education, and work activity tend to have significant relations with noise
14 perception (Yu and Kang, 2008). Table 9 shows that older people have lower
15 satisfaction with some features of green spaces and higher annoyance with some sound
16 sources. Also, as shown by recent studies (Dadvand et al., 2016; Dzhambov and
17 Dimitrova, 2015), there is a positive correlation between age and the frequency of noise
18 effects and, in some cases, this correlation is very significant ($p < 0.001$). In addition,
19 age is related to significant differences in work activity, because it is retirees who have
20 the worst perceptions of the features of green spaces and the noise in them.

	Sociodemographic characteristics				Urban green space use							
	Age	Sex	Education	Work activity	Reading	Taking children out	Relaxing	Exercising	Walking	Talking	Daily duration	Years visiting the park
	R ^a	X ^{2b}	R ^a	X ^{2b}	R ^a							
Satisfaction												
Cleanliness	-0.21 ^{***}	-	0.19 ^{**}	9.7 [*]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Air quality	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.26 ^{***}	-	-	-	-	-
Noise	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.19 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	-
Aesthetic	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.18 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	-
Safety	-0.24 ^{***}	-	-	17.8 ^{**}	-	-	-0.19 ^{**}	-	-	-	-0.20 ^{**}	-0.31 ^{***}
User	-	-	-	-	-	0.15 [*]	0.16 [*]	-0.40 ^{***}	0.22 ^{***}	0.55 ^{***}	0.23 ^{***}	-
Conservation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Location	-	-	-	-	-	0.18 [*]	-	-	-	-	-	-
Size	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.16 [*]	-	-	-	-
Shade	-	-	-	12.2 [*]	-	-	0.22 ^{***}	0.21 ^{**}	-	-	-	-
Groves	-	-	-	11.9 [*]	-	-	0.19 ^{**}	0.25 ^{***}	-	-	-	-
All features	-0.30 ^{***}	-	0.14 [*]	14.2 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sound sources annoyance												
Construction	0.24 ^{***}	-	-0.14 [*]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.31 ^{***}	0.16 [*]
Screams	0.17 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.19 ^{**}	-	0.17 ^{**}	0.20 ^{**}	-
Animals	-	-	-0.24 ^{***}	-	0.15 [*]	-	0.21 ^{***}	-	0.22 ^{***}	0.14 [*]	-	-
Maintenance	0.29 ^{***}	-	-	28.8 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	0.14 [*]	-	0.21 ^{***}	-
Road traffic	-	-	-	-	0.19 ^{**}	-	0.19 ^{**}	-0.15 [*]	-	-	-	-
Children	0.15 ^{**}	9.6 [*]	-	-	-	0.29 ^{***}	-	-0.16 [*]	0.16 [*]	0.17 ^{**}	0.12 [*]	0.20 ^{**}
Water	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.15 [*]	-	-	-	-
Overall	0.28 ^{***}	-	-0.16 ^{**}	30.1 [*]	-	-	0.15 [*]	-0.21 ^{**}	0.16 ^{**}	-	0.12 [*]	-
Frequency affected activities												
Talking	0.19 ^{***}	-	-0.19 ^{**}	18.8 ^{***}	-	-	-	-0.34 ^{**}	0.24 ^{***}	0.38 ^{***}	0.17 ^{**}	0.25 ^{***}
Reading	-	-	-	-	0.84 ^{***}	-	0.17 [*]	-	-	-	-	0.21 ^{**}
Relaxing	-	-	-	-	0.19 ^{**}	-	0.20 ^{**}	-0.14 [*]	0.17 ^{**}	0.14 [*]	-	0.18 ^{**}
Walking	0.31 ^{***}	-	-0.26 ^{***}	22.7 ^{***}	-	-	0.15 [*]	-0.23 ^{***}	0.25 ^{***}	0.20 ^{**}	0.25 ^{***}	-
Exercising	0.28 ^{***}	-	-0.19 ^{**}	24.9 ^{***}	-	-	-	0.62 ^{***}	-0.30 ^{***}	-	-	-0.21 ^{**}
										0.47 ^{***}		
Frequency emotions												
Irritability	0.23 ^{***}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.26 ^{***}	-	-	0.21 ^{***}	0.16 [*]
Anxiety	0.22 ^{***}	-	-0.13 [*]	12.5 [*]	0.18 [*]	-	0.14 [*]	-	0.15 [*]	-	0.22 ^{***}	-
Disorientation	0.13 [*]	-	-	-	0.19 [*]	-	-	-	0.16 [*]	-	-	-
Fear	0.18 ^{**}	-	-0.17 ^{**}	21.8 ^{***}	-	-	-	-0.26 ^{***}	-	0.15 [*]	-	-
Earache	0.30 ^{***}	-	-	20.3 ^{***}	-	-	-	-0.20 ^{**}	-	-	0.21 ^{***}	0.18 ^{**}
Frequency actions												
Increasing conversation volume	0.22 ^{***}	-	-0.17 ^{**}	18.7 ^{***}	-	-	-	-0.36 ^{***}	0.18 ^{**}	-0.23 ^{**}	-	-
Interrupting the conversation	0.21 ^{***}	-	-0.21 ^{***}	17.8 ^{**}	-	-	-	-0.22 ^{***}	0.20 ^{**}	0.22 ^{**}	0.16 [*]	-
Leaving the site	-	-	-	-	0.22 ^{**}	-	0.17 ^{**}	-	0.18 ^{**}	-	0.19 ^{**}	0.25 ^{***}
Leaving the green space	0.17 ^{**}	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.14 [*]	-	0.16 [*]	-

- 1 ^a Correlation coefficient (Kendall's tau-b).
- 2 ^b Chi-squared test
- 3 * Significant at p < 0.05.
- 4 ** Significant at p < 0.01.
- 5 *** Significant at p < 0.001.
- 6 - Non-significant correlation (p > 0.05).

7 **Table 9.** Relationships among sociodemographic characteristics, green-space use, and
8 satisfaction with the features, noise annoyance, and effects of noise in urban green
9 spaces.

	Sociodemographic characteristics			
	Age	Sex	Education	Work activity
	R ^a	X ^{2b}	R ^a	X ^{2b}
Urban green space use				
Reading	–	–	–	–
Taking children out	–	12.9 ^{***}	–	23.1 ^{***}
Relaxing	0.14 [*]	–	–0.29 ^{***}	21.6 ^{***}
Exercising	–0.22 ^{***}	11.9 ^{***}	0.24 ^{***}	17.3 ^{**}
Walking	0.32 ^{***}	–	–0.29 ^{***}	35.9 ^{***}
Talking	0.14 [*]	–	–0.29 ^{***}	32.3 ^{***}
Daily duration	–	–	–0.13 [*]	23.8 ^{***}
Years visiting the park	0.39 ^{***}	–	–0.23 ^{***}	29.4 ^{***}

1 ^a Correlation coefficient (Kendall’s tau–b).

2 ^b Chi-squared test

3 ^{*} Significant at p < 0.05.

4 ^{**} Significant at p < 0.01.

5 ^{***} Significant at p < 0.001.

6 – Non-significant correlation (p > 0.05).

7 **Table 10.** Relationships between sociodemographic characteristics and frequency of the
8 type of use of green spaces.

9 Educational level has a positive correlation with satisfaction with the features of green
10 spaces and a negative correlation with annoyance and effects of noise. This result differs
11 from the results obtained in other studies, in which people with a higher education level
12 felt slightly more annoyed (Miedema and Vos, 1999). This difference can be explained
13 by the correlation between the educational level and the uses of the green space (see
14 Table 10). It can be seen that people with a higher educational level use the green space
15 for exercise more frequently and the users who perform physical activity in the green
16 space indicate that they are annoyed or affected by the noise in the green space with
17 lower frequency, as shown in Table 9.

18 Next, the relationships between the frequency of the type of use by users and their
19 perceptions of the features of the green space and the existing noise are analysed. The

1 results of these relationships may be relevant for designing a green space for certain
2 uses.

3 It is interesting to point out that the users who most frequently perform a certain activity
4 in the green space also indicate that noise affects them more frequently. Thus, users who
5 perform an activity more frequently show a greater sensitivity to noise.

6 Reading and relaxing are activities that need quiet environments for good development.
7 In addition, relaxing is an important activity to ease the stress to which the inhabitants
8 of current cities are submitted. There are numerous studies that relate stress to serious
9 health problems (Agyei et al., 2014; Grazuleviciene et al., 2017; Harris et al., 2017).

10 Hence the existence of green areas that are properly designed for carrying out this
11 activity is important. Users who most frequently perform relaxing and reading activities
12 have significant correlations with those who indicate that noise frequently affects
13 reading and relaxation activities, respectively. However, perhaps because of the low
14 percentage of users who read in Cáceres green spaces (see Table 2), only users who
15 frequently go there to relax show significant relationships with the features of the green
16 space. They have a positive correlation with satisfaction with air quality, absence of
17 noise, aesthetics, users, shade, and groves (see Table 9) and a negative correlation with
18 the registered sound values (see Table 11). Therefore, the quality of all these features
19 and the presence of low sound levels should be considered in the design of green spaces
20 to allow relaxing activities to carry out properly. Sound indicators related to background
21 noise and to a high-frequency spectral composition are those without a significant
22 correlation with the frequency of use of relaxation activity (see Table 11). However,
23 sound indicators related to high-intensity sources have a significant correlation.
24 Considering the complete area of green spaces, these sound sources will correspond to
25 road traffic or to animals, in particular to dogs barking. In addition, the annoyance with

1 these sound sources is positively correlated with users who frequently go to green
 2 spaces to relax and read (see Table 9).

Sound indicator	Urban green space use	
	Relaxing	Walking
L _{Cpeak}	-0.52 ^{**}	-0.07 ^{n.s.}
L _{Amax}	-0.41 [*]	-0.29 ^{n.s.}
L _{A1}	-0.53 ^{***}	-0.41 [*]
L _{A5}	-0.54 ^{***}	-0.38 [*]
L _{A10}	-0.51 ^{**}	-0.34 [*]
L _{A50}	-0.42 [*]	-0.30 ^{n.s.}
L _{A90}	-0.25 ^{n.s.}	-0.24 ^{n.s.}
L _{A95}	-0.24 ^{n.s.}	-0.24 ^{n.s.}
L _{A99}	-0.22 ^{n.s.}	-0.23 ^{n.s.}
L _{Amin}	-0.17 ^{n.s.}	-0.19 ^{n.s.}
L _{Aeq}	-0.45 ^{**}	-0.33 [*]
L _{eq} ^b	-0.74 ^{***}	-0.25 ^{n.s.}
L _{Aeq} ^b	-0.50 ^{**}	-0.10 ^{n.s.}
Loudness ^b	-0.47 ^{**}	-0.12 ^{n.s.}
Sharpness ^b	-0.02 ^{n.s.}	-0.15 ^{n.s.}

3 ^{*} Significant at $p \leq 0.05$.
 4 ^{**} Significant at $p \leq 0.01$.
 5 ^{***} Significant at $p \leq 0.001$.
 6 ^{n.s.} Non-significant correlation ($p > 0.05$).
 7 ^b Registered with a binaural device

8 **Table 11.** Spearman's correlation coefficients among green space use data and sound
 9 indicators at the sampling point.

10 As previously mentioned, children are most frequently taken to green spaces by women
 11 and their annoyance with the sound source arising from children is significantly greater
 12 than that of men. Also, those who frequently take children to green spaces are positively
 13 correlated with satisfaction with the other green space users and the location of green
 14 spaces. The location of green spaces is important for those who frequently take children
 15 because they cannot walk long distances. Also, an adequate relationship with other
 16 users is important for this activity.

1 The frequency of the activity of speaking has a positive correlation with user
2 satisfaction because of the importance of the presence of other users. People who
3 perform this activity in green spaces have positive correlations with the degree of
4 annoyance with sound sources: screams, animals, and children. Also the frequency of
5 this activity is positively correlated with some of the most frequent effects of noise:
6 talking, walking, feeling afraid, and interrupting the conversation.

7 With respect to the temporality data (number of years for which the user has visited the
8 green space and daily frequency), there is a relation with age or work activity (retired).
9 Therefore, some correlation results obtained in Table 9 are explained. However, it is
10 important to highlight that daytime has a significant positive correlation with the overall
11 annoyance with noise and with some of the effects of the higher-frequency noise.

12 Nowadays, cities around the world are also investing in urban green spaces to increase
13 the physical activity of citizens (Shanahan et al., 2015; Szeremeta and Zannin, 2013).
14 This is ever more important because a sedentary lifestyle has become increasingly
15 prevalent in the twenty-first century. The main physical activities carried out by users of
16 Cáceres green spaces are running and walking. In addition, these urban green spaces
17 have outdoor gyms. Users who frequently use green spaces to exercise have positive
18 correlations with the satisfaction with size, shade, and groves. These features benefit the
19 development of running activity, which is the main exercise performed by users.
20 However, these users have a negative correlation with user satisfaction. In that sense,
21 the fact that these environments do not have specific circuits allowing users to run far
22 away from other users may have an influence. A very relevant aspect is that users who
23 frequently perform exercise have a negative correlation with the perception of the
24 annoyance and effects of noise. Therefore, noise is not perceived negatively by these
25 users. However, walking activity has a positive correlation with the annoyance with

1 sound sources and the frequency of noise effects except for sports. Users who frequently
2 go to green spaces to walk, as well as those who go to relax, have a significant
3 correlation with the overall annoyance with noise sources. In fact, users who walk avoid
4 places with high sound levels in terms of L_{Aeq} (indicator represented in noise maps) and
5 the statistical sound indicators L_{A1} , L_{A5} , and L_{A10} , which are related to discontinuous
6 and intense sound sources, as shown in Table 11. Walking activity generates health
7 benefits and improves the quality of life (Yu et al., 2017). In fact, sustainable urban
8 design uses the "walkability" concept. In this study, walking frequency has a positive
9 correlation with the age of the users and also a significant difference in the case of
10 retirees (see Table 10). Regular performance of walking activity in old age effectively
11 prevents the onset and development of chronic diseases and helps maintain a good
12 quality of life (Ikenaga et al., 2017; Van Cauwenberg et al., 2016). This is important as
13 the population of older adults is rapidly growing worldwide. Therefore, noise is a factor
14 that should be considered in the design of green spaces.

15 **4. Conclusions**

16 The analysis of urban green spaces is important for their management and future design.
17 These areas need to be conserved and/or improved due to the social, environmental, and
18 economic functions they have in the urban environment. A study was carried out in
19 Cáceres green spaces by means of surveys and sound measurements. The analysis of
20 user satisfaction with the features of urban green spaces leads to the following
21 conclusions:

- 22 - Users show satisfaction levels of “quite satisfied” to “very satisfied” with regard to
23 the features of green spaces except for the aspects related to environmental

1 contamination such as air quality and noise. These environmental features have the
2 highest significant relationship with the overall satisfaction with the green space.

3 - Noise satisfaction is the only studied feature of green spaces that has not increased in
4 the last six years. That fact could be the reason why the increase in overall
5 satisfaction with green spaces over these years is not significant.

6 - Together with the satisfaction with other users, conservation, and shade, noise
7 satisfaction correctly predicts 71.4% of the variability of overall satisfaction with
8 green spaces.

9 The importance that users gave to noise satisfaction in the overall satisfaction with
10 green spaces was the reason for carrying out an analysis of the contribution of sound
11 sources to the perception of the sound environment and the study of its possible effects.

12 The analysis yielded the following conclusions:

13 - Noise sources in Cáceres green spaces produce a low level of annoyance among the
14 users, below that estimated in other urban areas with a similar level of sound
15 exposure. Also, as in other urban areas, road traffic is the most annoying sound
16 source and is also the sound source with the most significant correlation with both
17 overall annoyance and the registered sound indicators.

18 - As happens with the annoyance with noise sources, noise effects are low. The
19 activities of talking and walking, emotions of fear and irritability, and the action of
20 interrupting the conversation are most frequently affected by noise. Also, these
21 effects have the highest significant correlation with the overall annoyance.

22 - The equivalent continuous sound level (dB) and sharpness (acum) have a greater
23 significant correlation with the perception of noise by users. Therefore, this result
24 may indicate the importance of the sound spectrum for the improvement of the

1 features of the sound landscape in environments with low sound levels and
2 consequently low noise effects.

3 Finally, when relating the perception of the environment with sociodemographic
4 characteristics and the use of green spaces, the following conclusions emerge:

5 - The type of use of green spaces shows significant differences according to gender
6 and education level. Women take children to green spaces more often than men and
7 users with a higher educational level have a significant relation with greater
8 frequency of exercising in green spaces. These differences influence the perception
9 of sound sources. Women show higher annoyance with the sound source coming
10 from children, and educational level has a negative correlation with the perception of
11 noise.

12 - The activities of running, relaxing, and walking are essential to decrease health
13 problems associated with stress and a sedentary lifestyle among the population. In
14 this study, three conclusions can be drawn:

15 • Size, shade, and groves benefit running activity, but noise is not a relevant
16 factor. However, the negative correlation between running activity and user
17 satisfaction indicates the need for these environments to have specific circuits
18 for running far away from the influence of other users.

19 • Walking activity is the most frequent use of green spaces. The sites in green
20 spaces with high noise levels show a significant decrease in the frequency of
21 walking activity. Therefore, noise is a fundamental factor that should be
22 considered in the design of green spaces in which this activity is properly
23 developed.

- 1 • Air quality, shade, groves, the absence of noise, and aesthetics are significantly
2 related to the frequency with which users go to green spaces to relax. Also,
3 relaxation activity has a high correlation with noise level, especially with L_{eq}
4 (dB). Consequently, if urban green spaces must have a relaxation function, their
5 design should consider noise as an essential factor.

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